

Regulation of On-Farm Processing of Animal Products to Add Value and Stimulate Local Economies

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Sheep of the Churra Galega Bragançana breed

The shepherds of Churra Galega Bragançana sheep and Preta de Montêsinho goats in the mountains of north-eastern Portugal are facing increasing challenges due to market volatility and rural depopulation. These indigenous breeds, recognised for their hardiness and the quality of their products - meat, milk, wool and skin - offer great potential for processing products with added value, but national regulatory frameworks are often restrictive, limiting the economic viability of farms. Article 1, Chapter 1, point 3 of Regulation (EC) No 852/2004 allows Member States to establish national rules for the direct sale of small quantities of primary products to the final consumer or to local trade. Adapting these provisions to the context of small ruminants can facilitate on-farm processing and local sales, guaranteeing food safety and consumer protection. The recommendations include simplifying licences for small family units, supporting mobile slaughtering and processing units, and training in artisanal production techniques such as cheese production, wool finishing and leather tanning. Processing goat and lamb meat, as well as high-quality cheese and wool, can increase profit margins by up to 60 per cent while preserving biodiversity and cultural heritage. Implementing these measures can revitalise disadvantaged rural economies, promote sustainable agricultural practices and empower farmers to retain value locally. It also boosts family employment, consolidating families and strengthening social resilience. Valuing family labour ensures the transmission of knowledge and strengthens community ties, which are essential for rural sustainability. This regulatory model is an example of how to support small farming communities while complying with food safety and hygiene standards.

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